

Reversed-phase Extraction Chromatographic Studies of Lead with High Molecular Weight Carboxylic Acid and its Analytical Applications

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A selective method is proposed for the extraction and separation of microgram amounts of lead(II) from ammonium acetate-acetic acid solution with high molecular weight carboxylic acid, SRS-100. From a critical study of pH, stripping agents, exchange capacity of the exchanger and breakthrough capacity with respect to lead, the optimum conditions have been identified. The proposed method permits separation of lead from binary, ternary, i.e. multicomponent mixtures with metal ions commonly associated with lead, and the determination of lead in real samples.

Recently lead pollution in the environment is increasing rapidly. Separation of trace level toxicant (lead) possesses challenging problem to the analytical chemists. Extraction of lead(II) with naphthenic acid¹, capric acid², *N*¹,*N*²-diphenylbenzamide (HDPBA)³ has been reported. The separation of lead(II) from few elements with versatic acids in benzene^{4,5}, diethyl dithiocarbamate⁶, and potassium ethyl xanthate in carbon tetrachloride⁷ have been studied. The separation of lead with bis(2-ethyl hexyl)phosphate⁸ and a mixture of aliquat 336 and titan yellow⁹ by reversed-phase technique has been reported, but the systematic study on extraction chromatography of lead(II) with organic liquid cation exchanger (SRS-100) is lacking. This study reports the systematic work on extraction chromatography of lead(II) with high molecular weight carboxylic acid, SRS-100.

Results and Discussion

The pH ranges for the extraction of lead (41.08 µg) with SRS-100 were ascertained by carrying out the extractions between pH 2.5–6.0. The optimum pH range for quantitative extraction of Pb^{II} was 5.5–6.0. Flow rates of 0.5–2.5 ml min⁻¹ during extraction showed the complete retention of Pb^{II} in the column.

Result shows that the stripping of Pb^{II} was completed with 1.0 M HNO₃, 1.50 M HCl and 2.50 M CH₃COOH. It was found that 1.0 M HNO₃ gave the best stripping, hence it was used as eluant in further steps of experiments.

Breakthrough capacity of silica gel coated with SRS-100 was determined. It was observed that the leakage started at pH 5.5 and 6.0 after passing 15 and 19 ml of lead solution (1.8 mg/ml) respectively. The maximum amount of Pb^{II} loaded in SRS-100 on silica gel (1.005 g) at pH 5.5 and 6.0 were 27.00 and 34.20 mg respectively.

Separation of Pb^{II} from binary mixtures : At pH 5.5, Mg^{II}, Cr^{III}, Mn^{II}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Pd^{II}, Ag^I, Cd^{II}, Sn^{II}, rare earths (La^{III}, Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Sm^{III}, Gd^{III}, Dy^{III}) and actinides mainly U^{VI} were not extracted along with Pb^{II}, i.e. they passed through the column with the mobile phase. Later

extracted Pb^{II} was stripped from the column with 1 M HNO₃ and estimated spectrophotometrically. The separation of Pb^{II} from binary mixture containing Cu^{II}, Zr^{IV} and Th^{IV} along with Pb^{II} was achieved by passing the mixture through the column at pH 5.5 with the help of specific eluent. After extraction, in all these cases excepting Zr^{IV}, the diverse ion was stripped first from the column with specific stripping agents, e.g. Cu^{II} was eluted with 0.02 M HNO₃ and Th^{IV} with a mixture (1 : 1, v/v) of 0.2 M HNO₃ and 0.2 M NaNO₃ followed by stripping of Pb^{II} with 1 M HNO₃. In case of Pb^{II} and Zr^{IV}, lead(II) was eluted first with 1 M HNO₃ followed by stripping Zr^{IV} with 8 M HNO₃. The separation of Pb^{II} from Fe^{III} was done by passing the mixture through the column at pH 2.7, where Pb^{II} passed through the column with the mobile phase but Fe^{III} was extracted. Later Fe^{III} was stripped from the column with 0.5 M H₂SO₄. After separation, Pb^{II} was estimated spectrophotometrically.

Separation of Pb^{II} from synthetic multicomponent mixtures : In order to assess the possible analytical applications the proposed method has been applied to separate Pb^{II} from several synthetic mixtures containing different metal ions along with Pb^{II}. In almost all the cases quantitative extraction and separation have been achieved.

Pb^{II} was separated from U^{VI} and Th^{IV} by passing the mixture through the column at pH 5.5, only U^{VI} passed through the column with the mobile phase but Th^{IV} and Pb^{II} were extracted. After extraction Th^{IV} was stripped first from the column with a mixture (1 : 1, v/v) of 0.2 M HNO₃ and 0.2 M NaNO₃ then Pb^{II} with 1 M HNO₃.

Synthetic mixture containing Dy^{III}, Th^{IV} and Pb^{II} in different proportions was passed through the column at pH 5.5. The extracted Th^{IV} was eluted first with a mixture (1 : 1, v/v) of 0.2 M HNO₃ and 0.2 M NaNO₃ followed by Pb^{II} with 1 M HNO₃.

Separation of U^{VI}, Pb^{II} and Zr^{IV} was achieved by passing the mixture through the column at pH 5.5. At this condition only U^{VI} passed through the column with the mobile phase but rest of the metal ions were extracted. After ex-

TABLE 1—SEPARATION OF Pb^{II} FROM SYNTHETIC MIXTURES*

Pb^{II} taken = 41.08 µg, Column = 1.0 × 7.5 cm, Flow rate = 1 ml min⁻¹, pH values = 5.5

Sl. no.	Cation	Weight added/ (recovered) µg	Relative error %	Eluent used	Eluent volume ml
1.	U ^{VI}	3640 (3620)	-0.55	—	—
	Th ^{IV}	4640 (4660)	+0.43	(1 : 1) 0.2 M HNO ₃ - 0.2 M NaNO ₃	25
	Pb ^{II}	41.08 (40.70)	-0.93	1 M HNO ₃	20
2.	Dy ^{III}	3280 (3250)	-0.91	—	—
	Th ^{IV}	4640 (4670)	+0.65	(1 : 1) 0.2 M HNO ₃ - 0.2 M NaNO ₃	25
	Pb ^{II}	41.08 (40.60)	-1.16	1 M HNO ₃	20
3.	U ^{VI}	3640 (3610)	-0.82	—	—
	Pb ^{II}	41.08 (41.70)	+1.50	1 M HNO ₃	20
	Zr ^{IV}	3340 (3300)	-1.20	8 M HNO ₃	15
4.	Fe ^{III}	4560 (4520)	-0.88	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	25
	Cu ^{II}	3520 (3540)	+0.57	0.02 M HNO ₃	25
	Pb ^{II}	41.08 (40.80)	-0.68	1 M HNO ₃	20
5.	Fe ^{III}	4560 (4540)	-0.44	0.5 M H ₂ SO ₄	25
	Zn ^{II}	2450 (2460)	+0.40	—	—
	Cu ^{II}	3520 (3560)	+1.14	0.02 M HNO ₃	25
	Pb ^{II}	41.08 (40.50)	-1.41	1 M HNO ₃	20
6.	U ^{VI}	3640 (3600)	-1.09	—	—
	Th ^{IV}	4640 (4680)	+0.86	(1 : 1) 0.2 M HNO ₃ - 0.2 M NaNO ₃	25
	Pb ^{II}	41.08 (41.60)	+1.26	1 M HNO ₃	15
	Zr ^{IV}	3340 (3290)	-1.50	8 M HNO ₃	15

* Average of five determinations. For sl. nos. 4 and 5, pH = 2.7

traction Pb^{II} was stripped first with 1 M HNO₃ then Zr^{IV} with 8 M HNO₃.

Pb^{II} was separated from Fe^{III} and Cu^{II} by passing the mixture at pH 2.7 where only Fe^{III} was extracted. Fe^{III} was stripped with 0.5 M H₂SO₄. The effluent containing Cu^{II} and Pb^{II} was passed at pH 5.5, when both of them were extracted. Cu^{II} was eluted with 0.2 M HNO₃ then Pb^{II} with 1 M HNO₃.

Mixture containing Fe^{III}, Zn^{II}, Cu^{II} and Pb^{II} was passed through the column at pH 2.7 where only Fe^{III} was extracted and stripped with 0.5 M H₂SO₄. The effluent containing Zn^{II}, Cu^{II} and Pb^{II} was then passed at pH 5.5 when Zn^{II} passed through the column whereas Cu^{II} and Pb^{II} were

TABLE 2—ANALYSIS OF STANDARD SAMPLES FOR LEAD*

Sample and its Consumption	Certi- fied value %	Amount found %	Standard deviation	Coeff. of variation
Gunmetal (ITA Lab., 4382) (Cu, 76.53; Sn, 4.86; Sb, 0.53; Pb, 12.08; Fe, 0.15; Ni, 0.42; Zn, 5.41; P, 0.011%)	12.08	12.02	0.019	0.15
Brass (5 g) (Cu, 67.4; Sn, 1.09; Zn, 28.6; Pb, 2.23; Ni, 0.33; Fe, 0.32; P, 0.01)	2.23	2.19	0.020	0.91
Solder (11 g) (Sn, 59.9; Pb, 40.0; Fe, 0.002; Sb, 0.03)	40.00	39.50	0.051	0.13

* Average of six determinations.

extracted. Cu^{II} was stripped with 0.02 M HNO₃ followed by Pb^{II} with 1 M HNO₃.

Mixture of U^{VI}, Th^{IV}, Pb^{II} and Zr^{IV} was separated by passing it through the column at pH 5.5 where only U^{VI} passed through the column. Th^{IV} was then eluted with a mixture (1 : 1, v/v) of 0.2 M HNO₃ and 0.2 M NaNO₃ followed by Pb^{II} with 1 M HNO₃ and Zr^{IV} with 8 M HNO₃. The results of separations are given in Table 1.

Analysis of lead in 'real' samples : The proposed method was successfully applied to the separation and determination of lead in lead based alloys. The results are in good agreement with the certified value (Table 2).

The proposed method is simple, rapid, selective and gives clean separation of lead from elements like Cr, Fe, Cu, Zn, Cd, Zr, Th, U and lanthanides.

Experimental

An ECIL 5652 A pH-meter with a combined glass electrode, Backman DU-6 and ECIL GS 5700 A spectrophotometer, and a chromatographic column (i.d. 1.0 cm) of borosil glass were used.

The liquid cation exchanger, SRS-100 (Shell Chemical), a high molecular weight carboxylic acid (C₁₅-C₁₆), was used as such. A stock solution of Pb^{II} (4.50 mg ml⁻¹) was prepared from lead nitrate (A.R.) in demineralized water and standardized¹⁰. A solution containing 41.08 µg ml⁻¹ of Pb^{II} was prepared through dilution. Buffer solutions of different pH were prepared from 0.2 M acetic acid and 0.2 M sodium acetate/ammonium acetate solutions in proper ratio.

Ion exchange material : Silica gel (30-120 mesh, B.D.H.) was rendered hydrophobic by exposing it to the vapor of dimethyldichlorosilane in nitrogen atmosphere¹¹. 1 ml of dimethyldichlorosilane was adequate for 10 g of silica gel and 1 g of hydrophobic gel could take up about 0.7 ml of SRS-100. For column work, 7.5 cm bed was prepared and washed with 4 M HCl to remove excess of or-

ganic solvent. Silica gel was preferred as the support for SRS-100 because it being porous and retained a considerable amount of extractant. Each column was usable for at least 20 cycles without loss of extraction capacity.

Exchange capacity : The exchange capacity of the exchanger was determined at different temperatures by measuring the number of miligram equivalents of sodium ion absorbed by 1 g of dry exchanger in the hydrogen form¹². The exchange capacity of the prepared exchanger was found to be 1.70 meq of H⁺/g at 25°.

General extraction procedure : SRS-100 (3.0 g) impregnated on silica gel was loaded in a chromatographic column (1.0 × 7.5 cm) and pH of the exchanger bed was adjusted with 0.2 M acetic acid and 0.2 M ammonium acetate. An aliquot of solution containing 41.08 µg of Pb^{II} was mixed with 0.2 M acetic acid (10 ml), its pH was adjusted to 5.5 and passed through the column. After extraction Pb^{II} was stripped with different mineral acids. Five fractions (each of 4 ml) were collected and the amount of Pb^{II} from each fraction was determined spectrophotometrically with arsenazo III as chromo-genic reagent at 605 nm¹³.

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References

1. A. W. FLETCHER and D. S. FLETT, "Solvent Extraction of Metals", eds. H. A. C. MCKAY, T. V. HEALY, I. L. JENKINS, and A. NAYLON, Macmillan, London, 1966, p. 359.
2. N. NAKASUKA, M. NAKAI, and M. TANAKA, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1970, **32**, 3667.
3. K. SATYANARAYANA and R. K. MISHRA, *Anal. Chem.*, 1974, **46**, 1609.
4. U. S. RAY, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1982, **21**, 444.
5. U. S. RAY and S. C. MODAK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1984, **61**, 245.
6. H. IRTH, G. J. DEJONG, U. A. BRIMKMAN, and R. W. FERL, *Anal. Chem.*, 1987, **59**, 98.
7. A. K. CHAKRAVARTI, A. DATTAGUPTA, T. CHAKRABARTY, D. C. MUKHERJEE, and S. P. MAULIK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1993, **70**, 230.
8. Yi. Yu. VIN and S. M. KHOPKAR, *Anal. Lett.*, 1990, **23**, 635.
9. R. KOJIAN, *Analyst (London)*, 1982, **117**, 741.
10. R. PRIBIL, "Chelometry, Basic Determinations", Chemapol, Prague, 1961.
11. R. B. HEDDUR and S. M. KHOPKAR, *J. Liquid Chromatogr.*, 1983, **8**, 95.
12. A. BANDYOPADHYAY and U. S. ROY, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1996, **73**, 177.
13. Y. MICHAYLOVA and N. KULEVA, *Talanta*, 1980, **27**, 63.